

EVALUATION OF RESIDUAL STRAIN OF FIBRES IN MATRIX RESIN DURING CURE PROCESS BY OPTICAL FIBRE SENSORS

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SUMMARY

Strain of embedded fibres in matrix resin during cure was evaluated by optical fibre strain sensors. Several temperature conditions were employed for molding resin. FE viscoelastic analyses were also conducted to calculate strain of the embedded optical fibres. These results showed that the temperature histories strongly affected residual strain of the embedded fibres.

Keywords: Cure Monitoring, Optical Fibre Sensors, Residual Strain measurements, FBG sensor, Viscoelastic analysis

INTRODUCTION

Optimization and control of moulding conditions of FRP are key technologies for manufacturing high quality products. For the purpose, many kinds of cure monitoring methods of FRP moulding such as a differential thermal analysis (DTA) or a Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) have been investigated. However, most of their methods can be applied only to small sample even though an integral molding method is employed to manufacture large and complex-shaped FRP products in recent years. Recently, new cure monitoring methods which enable *in situ* monitoring have been proposed by employing small and embeddable sensors. Among the suitable sensors for cure monitoring, fibre optic sensors are most promised because of small size, flexibility and high sensitivity.

There are many kinds of fibre optic sensors which can measure temperature, pressure, cure index or strain. Especially, strain measurement using a fibre optic strain sensor is only method to monitor changes in FRP shape during molding. This technique is very important for manufacturing high quality products because residual deformation of FRP produced by large curing and thermal strains of matrix resin causes significant problems such as residual stress or spring-back [1-3].

In this paper, residual strain profiles of embedded FBG (Fibre Bragg Grating) optical fibre strain sensors in epoxy matrix resin were measured during cure and post-cure processes. Several cure conditions were employed to investigate effect of a cure-profile on final residual strain. Furthermore, an FE viscoelastic analysis was conducted in order to explain the experimental results.

MEASUREMENTS OF RESIDUAL STRAIN IN RESIN DURING CURE

Materials

As shown in Table 1, a bisphenol-A epoxy resin (Epikote 801 N, Japan Epoxy Resins, Co. Ltd.) with curing agent of epicure 3080, where the mixture ratio was 100:45 in weight, was used for the present study. Glass transition temperature of the cured resin was 52 °C.

Table 1. Base resin and curing agent.

	Compounding ratio	Product name	Type	Manufacturer
Base resin	1	Epikote 801N	Bisphenol A	Japan Epoxy Resins, Co., Ltd.
Curing agent	0.45	Epicure 3080	modified aliphatic polyamine	Japan Epoxy Resins, Co., Ltd.

Moulding conditions

In the present study, three kinds of temperature profiles were used for moulding resin as shown in Figure 1 and Tables 2. Before deciding these profiles, a DOC (degree of cure) curve was measured by a refractive index sensor at condition of constant temperature of 40 °C. As shown in Fig.1, the temperature profiles were composed of cure cycle of 40 °C and post-cure cycle of 100 °C. Length of the cure cycles of 40 °C was decided as DOC reached to 60%, 80% and 90% at the end of the cycles. Therefore, we called these three temperature profiles 60% cure, 80% cure and 90% cure in this paper.

Figure 1. Three moulding temperature profiles used for experiments and a DOC curve measured by a refractive index sensor at condition of constant temperature of 40°C.

Table 2. Temperature step of cure cycles.

Stage	60% cure	80% cure	90% cure
1	900	720	900
2	18000	36000	46800
3	Natural cooling	Natural cooling	Natural cooling
4	3960	3600	3600
5	18000	18000	18000
6	Natural cooling	Natural cooling	Natural cooling

Figure 2. Experimental setup for measuring residual strain of an FBG sensor embedded in resin during moulding.

Experimental method and sensor

In this experiment, single EBG sensor was embedded in resin. An FBG sensor has a periodical grating of refractive index which reflects narrow-band light when broad-band light is incident. Because a centre wavelength of the reflected narrow-band light is a function of a period of the grating, strain ε_3 and temperature shift ΔT can be calculated from the wavelength shift $\Delta\lambda$ using the following equation.

$$\frac{\Delta\lambda}{\lambda_0} = \left[1 - \frac{n_0^2}{2} \{ p_{12} - \nu_s (p_{11} + p_{12}) \} \right] (\varepsilon_3 - \alpha_s \Delta T) + \left(\alpha_s + \frac{1}{n_0} \frac{dn_0}{dT} \right) \Delta T. \quad (1)$$

Here, λ_0 is an initial centre wavelength, n_0 is an effective refractive index, p_{12} and p_{11} are Pockel's constants, ν_s and α_s are Poisson's ratio and thermal expansion coefficient of an optical fibre. Sensitivities of the sensor were experimentally obtained as

$$\left[1 - \frac{n_0^2}{2} \{p_{12} - \nu_s(p_{11} + p_{12})\} \right] = 0.7368, \left(\alpha_s + \frac{1}{n_0} \frac{dn_0}{dT} \right) = 6.138 \times 10^{-6}. \quad (2)$$

Figure 2 illustrates an experimental setup for measuring residual strain of an FBG sensor embedded in resin during moulding. The silicon mould size was 20×20×35mm. The FBG sensors were manufactured by Advanced Optics Solutions Inc. The initial wavelength was 1550 nm, the diameter was 125µm and the gauge length was 10 mm. An FBG sensor monitor unit (SF311A, Anritsu Co., Ltd.) was used for measuring wavelength shift. Temperature very near the embedded FBG sensor was also measured by an embedded thermo-couple. Using the equation (1), strain of the embedded optical fibre was calculated from measured wavelength shift and temperature shift.

Experimental results and discussions

The time histories of measured strain and temperature for three moulding temperature profiles were plotted against time in Fig.3. From the experimental results, it was found that the residual strains of 60% cure, 80% cure and 90% cure at the end of cure cycle 40°C (the stage 2) were 10 µε, -20 µε and -94 µε, respectively. It can be considered that these small compressive strains were caused by curing shrinkage although the strain transmissibility from the resin to the optical fibre was very low at low degree of cure. At the natural cooling (the stage 3), strains of 80% cure and 90% cure showed compressive strains of 192 µε and 451 µε because of thermal shrinkage of resin.

Strain profiles at the heating stage to 100 °C (the stage 4) showed tensile strain due to thermal expansion of the resin however the output strains of three results were different from each other. The results of the 60% cure condition showed very small strain of 122 µε, on the contrary, the strains of the 80% and 90% cure curves became 859 µε and 1214 µε at the end of the stage. At the constant temperature of 100 °C (the stage 5), very large compressive strains could be observed for all results. The strains became -890 µε, 129 µε and 723 µε at the end of the stage, respectively. The decrease of strains of 60%, 80% and 90% cure results, which means curing shrinkage of resin at post-cure process, were simply obtained as 1012 µε, 730 µε and 491 µε. These results showed that the 60% cure result generated larger curing shrinkage than the other two results because resin cured by the 60% cure profile had more residual epoxides at the start of the stage 5. Finally, residual strains of 60%, 80% and 90% cure results became -5952 µε, -5451 µε and -4200 µε after the cooling stage (the stage 6).

Figure 4 shows relationships between residual strain measured by FBG sensors and temperature during post-process. From the figure, it appeared that sensitivities of strain of the three results to temperature at the heating stage were very different however the residual strains generated at the stage 6 were almost the same. Therefore, it was found that the start timing of heating stage of post-cure process contributed strongly final residual strain after finishing all cure process.

Figure 3. Relationships between strain measured by FBG sensors, temperature and moulding time during epoxy cure process.

Figure 4. Relationships between residual strain measured by FBG sensors and temperature during post-process.

FEM ANALASYS AND RESULTS

Constitutive equation

A viscoelastic constitutive equation for general isotropic viscoelastic materials can be represented by

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}(t) = \int_0^{\tau(t)} 2G(\tau - \tau') \dot{\mathbf{e}} d\tau' + \mathbf{I} \int_0^{\tau(t)} K(\tau - \tau') \dot{\phi} d\tau', \quad (3)$$

$$\phi = \varepsilon_{11} + \varepsilon_{22} + \varepsilon_{33} \text{ and } \mathbf{e} = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - \frac{1}{3}\phi \mathbf{I} \quad (4)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is a stress tensor, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ is a mechanical strain tensor, \mathbf{e} is a deviatoric strain tensor, ϕ is a bulk strain, \mathbf{I} is a unit tensor, G is a shear modulus, K is a bulk modulus, t is real time and $\tau(t)$ is a reduced time as a function of temperature. The reduced time can be written using a temperature shift factor of resin $A_T(T)$ as

$$\tau(t) = \int_0^t \frac{dt'}{A_T(T(t'))}. \quad (5)$$

In the present paper, we supposed that moduli of resin varied during cure process and then the equation (3) was modified to represent viscoelastic constitutive equation of resin during moulding as follows.

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}(t) = \int_0^{\tau} 2G(\alpha, \tau - \tau') \dot{\mathbf{e}} d\tau' + \mathbf{I} \int_0^{\tau} K(\alpha, \tau - \tau') \dot{\phi} d\tau' \quad (6)$$

where α is degree of cure of resin which varies from zero to 1 during moulding process. The viscoelastic shear modulus $G(\alpha, t)$ of resin during cure process was defined by Prony series as

$$G(\alpha, t) = G_0 A_\alpha(\alpha) \left\{ 1 - \sum_{i=1}^{n_G} g_i (1 - e^{-t/\tau_i}) \right\} \quad (7)$$

where G_0 is an instantaneous shear modulus, A_α is a decrease index of shear modulus and g_i and τ_i are Prony parameters. On the other hand, it was supposed that the bulk modulus was constant during cure, that is,

$$K(\alpha, t) = K_0. \quad (8)$$

Here K_0 is an instantaneous bulk modulus. From the equations (6), (7) and (8), the following equations were obtained.

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}(t) = 2G_0 \left(\tilde{\mathbf{e}} - \sum_{i=1}^{n_G} g_i \tilde{\mathbf{e}}_i \right) + \mathbf{I} K_0 \phi, \quad (9)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{e}} = \int_0^{\tau(t)} A_\alpha(\alpha) \frac{d\mathbf{e}}{d\tau'} d\tau', \quad \tilde{\mathbf{e}}_i = \int_0^{\tau(t)} A_\alpha(\alpha) (1 - e^{-(\tau-\tau')/\tau_i}) \frac{d\mathbf{e}}{d\tau'} d\tau' \quad (10)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{e}}$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{e}}_i$ represent deviatoric elastic strain and viscoelastic strain, respectively. In this study, a stress tensor was numerically calculated by discrete equations of (9) and (10).

Material characteristics of resin

Most parameters necessary for calculation of viscoelastic response of resin during cure process were experimentally obtained in the present study. DOC of resin at arbitrary curing condition was calculated by the following Kamal's model [4].

$$\dot{\alpha} = (k_1 + k_2 \alpha^m) \times (1 - \alpha)^n, \quad (11)$$

$$k_1 = A_1 \exp\left(-\frac{E_1}{RT}\right), k_2 = A_2 \exp\left(-\frac{E_2}{RT}\right), \quad (12)$$

where R is gas constant, E_1 and E_2 are activation energies and m , n , A_1 and A_2 are material constants. These parameters were obtained by curve fitting the equation (11) to the experimental DOC curves as a function of temperature. The experimental curves were measured by DSC (Differential Scanning Calorimeter, Prys 1, Perkin-Elmer, Inc.). The obtained values were $m=0.35$, $n=1.71$, $A_1=188.15 \text{ s}^{-1}$, $A_2=3613.5 \text{ s}^{-1}$, $E_1= 48044 \text{ kcal/mol}$ and $E_2=44017 \text{ kcal/mol}$.

A temperature shift factor was defined by a WLF (Williams-Landell-Ferry) equation as follows.

$$-\log_{10} A_T = \frac{C_1^g (T - T_g)}{C_2^g + (T - T_g)}, \quad (13)$$

where $T_g = 52^\circ\text{C}$ is a glass transition temperature of resin, and $C_1^g=17.44$ and $C_2^g = 51.6$ were constants for polymers.

Prony parameters of epoxy resin (Epikote 801N+Epikure 3080) were experimentally measured. A master curve of shear compliance was obtained from data of creep tests conducted by a DMA (Dynamic Mechanical Analyzer, DMA7e, Perkin Elmer, Inc). Then, a master curve of shear modulus was calculated from the master curve of shear compliance using Laplace transform. The fitted Prony parameters to the master curve of shear modulus were shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Prony parameters of epoxy resin (Epikote 801N+Epikure 3080).

i	g_i	τ_i
1	0.7552	0.0006981
2	0.1398	0.01040
3	0.07937	0.1561
4	0.01641	3.583
5	0.005286	50.44
6	0.0009552	1186

The decrease index of shear modulus A_α was measured by a parallel-plate method using a rheometer (Visco Analyzer VAR100, Reologica Instruments, Inc.). The relaxation share modulus was measured as a function of cure cycle at the curing temperature condition of $+2.5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ for 30 minutes and 100°C for 180 minutes. The A_α curve was obtained by dividing measured shear modulus by converged shear modulus. Figure 5 shows the measured A_α curve as a function of degree of cure. From the figure, it was

found that the relationships between the A_α and degree of cure was almost linear and then the following relationship was used for the FE calculation in this paper.

$$A_\alpha(\alpha) = 3.179\alpha - 2.179 \quad (\alpha > 0.69). \quad (14)$$

Mechanical properties of the silica optical fiber and cured resin were tabulated in Table 4. Thermal expansion coefficients α_T were also shown in the table.

Figure 5. Relationships between degree of cure and decrease index of shear modulus A_α during cure process.

Table 4 Material properties of optical fibres and epoxy resin.

Glass (optical fiber)		Epoxy resin	
E_0 (MPa)	75000	G_0 (MPa)	978.26
ν	0.25	ν	0.38
α_T ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	0.5×10^{-6}	α_T ($^{\circ}\text{C}$, $T < 52$)	8.3×10^{-5}
		α_T ($^{\circ}\text{C}$, $T \geq 52$)	1.8×10^{-4}

FEM model and analysis

In order to evaluate strain of matrix resin, strain measured by the embedded FBG sensors was analyzed by a viscoelastic FEM. Figure 6 shows an axisymmetric model of the resin with an embedded FBG sensor. This model is a full model which expresses the experimental mould shown in Fig.2. Axisymmetric 8 nodes elements were used for meshing. Displacement of only one node of optical fibre along the symmetric axis was constrained.

Thermal strain $\alpha_T \Delta T$ and curing strain ε_c caused by curing shrinkage was applied to the resin part as follows;

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_t - (\alpha_T \Delta T + \varepsilon_c(\alpha)) \mathbf{I}. \quad (15)$$

where ϵ_t is a strain tensor at time t . The $\epsilon_c(\alpha(t))$ was experimentally measured by a dilatometer. The applied time-temperature profiles were the same as those tabulated in table 2 however the start time of calculation was shifted as the start DOC was 0.68 and the start temperature was 40 °C.

An FEM analyses were conducted by an FEM software ABAQUS 8.6. The discrete constitutive equation of resin was programmed by FORTRAN and assembled into a user-subroutine UMAT. In order to evaluate strain of matrix resin, average strain along the sensor part of the embedded FBG sensor was calculated.

Figure 6. An axisymmetric FEM model of resin with an embedded FBG sensor.

Results and discussion

Strains calculated by the FEM analysis were plotted against moulding time with experimental curves in Fig. 7. From the figure, it appeared that the behaviours of analytical curves agreed with the experimental curves quantitatively. The calculated results successfully represented that cancellation of thermal expansion by curing shrinkage affected resin expansion at the heating stage and curing shrinkage differs from each other at post-cure. Because curing shrinkage of resin is a function of degree of cure, it can be considered that the relationship between degree of cure and heating profile is the most significant factor to govern residual strain of embedded fibres. From these results, we have expected this method is available to predict residual strain of an embedded fibre in resin at any curing process. The difference between experiments and simulations was thought to be resulted in poor accuracy of measurement of curing shrinkage. For better prediction of strain profiles of embedded fibres during cure, more accurate profile of cure shrinkage of resin is necessary.

Figure 7. Measured and calculated strain profiles of embedded FBG sensors in epoxy resin during cure and post-cure processes.

CONCLUSION

In the present paper, residual strains in matrix resin were monitored by embedded FBG sensors as three different temperature profiles were applied during cure and post-cure processes. From the experimental results, it was found that the start timing of the post-cure process affected strongly final residual strain after all cure processes completed. In order to investigate the strain behaviour of resin, viscoelastic FE analysis was conducted for the experimental model. Most parameters used for calculation such as viscoelastic properties and a profile of curing shrinkage of resin were experimentally measured. From the results of FE analysis, it appeared that cancellation of thermal expansion by curing shrinkage affected strongly resin expansion at the heating stage of post-cure process therefore the relationship between degree of cure and heating profile is the most significant factor to govern residual strain of embedded fibres.

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